

“BLESSED ARE THE PEACEMAKERS”: DIETRICH BONHOEFFER’S UNDERSTANDING OF CHRISTIAN ETHICAL RESPONSIBILITY IN WARTIME AND THE ROLE OF PEACEMAKERS

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ABSTRACT: “Blessed Are the Peacemakers”: Dietrich Bonhoeffer’s Understanding of Christian Ethical Responsibility in Wartime and the Role of Peacemakers.

In the final years of his life, Dietrich Bonhoeffer lived through an extraordinarily difficult period: the Second World War (1939–1945). The atrocities committed against the Jewish people during this time are almost unimaginable—over six million Jews were systematically murdered in the Holocaust. Although Bonhoeffer was actively involved in the resistance against Adolf Hitler, including participating in plots to overthrow the Nazi regime, he consistently remained a proponent of peace. His ethical and theological reflections reveal a deep struggle between resistance and nonviolence. Today, as the world witnesses renewed conflict and moral crisis, Bonhoeffer’s understanding of war and the role of peacemakers remains profoundly relevant. This article seeks to explore his perspective on war and peace, and to reflect on how his thought speaks to the challenges of our own time.

Keywords: *Dietrich Bonhoeffer, Sermon on the Mount, war, ethic, Social Relation, peacemakers.*

Introduction

The desire to eradicate the people of Israel is not a modern phenomenon. Throughout history, figures like Haman (Esther 3–7)—whose intentions mirror those of later individuals and movements such as Adolf Hitler and,

more recently, Hamas—have pursued the destruction of the Jewish people. Yet time and again, these efforts have failed. As many believe, the God of Israel continues to defend them, rendering such ambitions ultimately futile. This reflection begins by examining the final period of Dietrich Bonhoeffer's life, marked by the turmoil of the Second World War. From there, it will explore his theological and ethical understanding of Christian conduct during wartime. Finally, it will consider Bonhoeffer's vision of peacemakers—those who, in his view, are called not merely to avoid conflict, but to actively work toward justice, reconciliation, and the flourishing of all people.

In an age marked by rising conflict, polarization, and the resurgence of antisemitism, revisiting the life and thought of Dietrich Bonhoeffer it is relevant. Bonhoeffer lived in a time when evil was institutionalized, truth was silenced, and the Church faced a choice: compliance or costly resistance. His moral clarity, theological depth, and willingness to act against injustice—while still upholding a commitment to peace—make his insights profoundly valuable for today's world. This work is important because it speaks directly to the ethical dilemmas we continue to face: How should Christians respond to violence and oppression? What does it mean to be a peacemaker in a world at war? Can resistance to evil coexist with a commitment to peace? Bonhoeffer wrestled with these questions not in theory, but in real life, under a brutal regime. Studying his understanding of war, peace, and the Christian's role in society challenges modern readers to reflect on their own responsibilities in the face of injustice. It also reclaims the radical meaning of Jesus' words: "Blessed are the peacemakers"—not as passive observers, but as courageous, morally grounded actors in the pursuit of justice and reconciliation.

Bonhoeffer in Context

Dietrich Bonhoeffer¹ was born on February 4, 1906, the sixth child of Karl and Paula Bonhoeffer. In 1912, the Bonhoeffer family relocated to Berlin, where Dietrich would spend much of his formative years. He later pursued theological studies at some of the most prestigious institutions of the time, beginning in Tübingen and continuing in Berlin. According to Samuel Randall, "The life of Dietrich Bonhoeffer, the German Luther-

1 Dietrich Bonhoeffer, *Costul uceniciei*, Oradea, Roua, 2020, p. 11.

an pastor, theologian, ecumenist, and political conspirator, has been described according to the different stages."² This perspective underscores the complexity and evolution of Bonhoeffer's thought and actions over the course of his life.

In the latter part of his life, Dietrich Bonhoeffer lived during a time of intense conflict and moral crisis: the Second World War. It was a period in which the Nazi regime in Germany sought to eliminate the Jewish people—Israel—at any cost. This genocidal campaign, later known as the Holocaust, was orchestrated at the highest levels of Nazi leadership. Heinrich Himmler is often credited as the architect of the plan, but it was Adolf Hitler who enforced it and gave it its chilling name: "the Final Solution to the Jewish problem."³ The roots of this ideology were embedded in a growing movement of anti-Semitism.⁴ The term itself was first coined by Wilhelm Marr, a German political agitator, in the context of a pamphlet promoting hostility toward Jews. Historian Jules Isaac⁵ clarifies that anti-Semitism should be understood in its "current, vulgar sense"—as prejudice or hostility toward Jews, whether viewed as a religious or racial group.⁶ Kenneth Marcus⁷ further explains that the ideology of anti-Semitism can take multiple forms. At times, it is framed in opposition to Judaism as a religion; at other times, it targets Jews as a supposed race. Ultimately, Marcus argues, anti-Semitism is not rooted purely in religious or racial theory—it is, more fundamentally, a process of transforming real individuals into a distorted and vilified image of "the Jews." This image, he notes, often relies on extreme forms of demonization and dehumanization.

Although many Jews appeared to belong to the bourgeois class due to their financial status, they were largely excluded from the broader processes of capitalist development.⁸ Political theorist Hannah Arendt

2 Samuel Randall, "Suffering as an Ecumenical Paradigm in Dietrich Bonhoeffer and Edith Stein," in *Theologica Wratislaviensia* T. 11. (2016): p. 126.

3 Joel Richardson, *Când un evreu va conduce lumea* (Cihei: Soli Deo Gloria, 2017), p. 165.

4 Jean-Christophe Attias, Esther Benbassa, „Antisemitism,” in *Dicționar de civilizație iudaică*, București, Univers Enciclopedic, 1997, pp. 26-27.

5 Jules Isaac, *Genesa antisemitismului*, București, Haseefer, 2014, p. 44.

6 Michael L. Brown, *Christian Antisemitism*, Lake Mary, Charisma House, 2001, p. 15.

7 Kenneth Marcus, *The Definition of Anti-Semitism*, Oxford, Oxford University Press, 2015, p. 192.

8 Hannah Arendt, *Originile Totalitarismului*, București, Humanitas, 2014, p. 27.

observed that “although their status was defined by the fact that they were Jews, they were only defined as such by their relationship with another class.”⁹ This suggests that Jewish identity, in the eyes of European society, was shaped not by internal economic roles but by external social positioning and marginalization. From a theological perspective, the Jewish people were set apart by divine calling, as taught in the Hebrew Scriptures (the Old Testament). God instructed them to live within society and contribute to its well-being, while remaining distinct in identity and purpose. As stated in Exodus 19:5–6, they were to be “a kingdom of priests and a holy nation,” set apart for a unique relationship with God and a mission within the world.

Anti-Jewish biases often gain political traction when they intersect with broader societal anxieties or when the perceived interests of Jewish communities appear to conflict with those of dominant social or political groups.¹⁰ Hannah Arendt observed that “German racial thought was taught in an effort to unite the people against foreign domination,”¹¹ which, in the context of Nazi ideology, was directed primarily against the Jewish population. Historically, anti-Semitism has often emerged as a politically mobilizing force during periods of crisis or transition. In ancient Egypt (Exodus 1), the Israelites were viewed as a growing threat to national stability. Similarly, at the time of Jesus’ birth in Roman-occupied Palestine (Matthew 1–2), fear of a rival “king” born among the Jews led to violent measures. During the Second World War, these age-old prejudices were once again weaponized—this time on an unprecedented scale—as anti-Semitism became a central political and ideological pillar of the Nazi regime.¹²

In 1933, the National Socialists came to power in Germany, ushering in a regime that quickly consolidated control over every aspect of society. Dietrich Bonhoeffer, early on, recognized the danger that this authoritarian movement posed. Reflecting on the psychology of the time, he wrote: “Man, and especially the young, will feel the need to accept the authority (Führer) of a leader over him, as long as he is not himself mature, strong, and responsible enough to carry out the demands claimed by this author-

9 Arendt, *Originile Totalitarismului*, p. 27.

10 Arendt, *Originile Totalitarismului*, p. 46.

11 Arendt, *Originile Totalitarismului*, p. 211.

12 Arendt, *Originile Totalitarismului*, p. 55.

ity."¹³ Bonhoeffer understood that the allure of a strong leader stemmed, in part, from a widespread crisis of personal and moral responsibility. One of the early and alarming policies of the Nazi state was the attempt to remove Jews from public life, including forcing their resignation from government and civil service roles. When the so-called "Aryan clause"—a law that barred individuals of Jewish descent from holding public office—was proposed for implementation within the Church, Bonhoeffer vehemently opposed it.¹⁴ He saw it not only as unjust, but as a direct violation of the Christian gospel and the integrity of the Church.

Bonhoeffer's view of Christian ethical behavior in wartime

Bonhoeffer believed that the actions of a disciple of Jesus should be grounded in love and beneficence toward others. These behaviors, he argued, must be practiced daily and reflected in the disciple's entire way of life. Geoff Broughton notes that "Bonhoeffer locates the enemy to be loved within the practical and everyday orbit of the disciples' lives," and emphasizes that Bonhoeffer "identifies the active dimension and goal of loving one's enemy."¹⁵ In the final phase of his life, Bonhoeffer insisted that a person must actively fight to do what is right, rejecting the notion that ethical dilemmas can remain unresolved indefinitely.¹⁶ Throughout his writings, he consistently emphasizes that ethical behavior must be rooted in concrete action rather than abstract theories or rigid moral systems. Hans van Hoogstraten, in his analysis of Bonhoeffer's poem *Who Am I?*, affirms that Bonhoeffer calls for the rejection of metaphysical constructs, including abstract catalogues of virtues. Even morality, when reduced to a doctrine of virtues, can become a tool of domination. For Bonhoeffer, justice stands as the central biblical virtue—but it must be enacted through the representation of Christ's powerlessness, not through displays of heavenly or institutional power. Without active participation in

13 Bonhoeffer, *Costul uceniciei*, pp. 12-13.

14 Bonhoeffer, *Costul uceniciei*, p. 13.

15 Geoff Broughton, "Interpretative strategies for Jesus' "Sermon on the Mount" (Matthew 5-7)," in *St. Mark's Review*, No. 227 February, (2014), p. 25.

16 Edmund Pincoffs, "Quandary Ethics", in *Revisions: Changing Perspectives in Moral Philosophy*, eds. Stanley Hauerwas and Alasdair MacIntyre, Notre Dame, University of Notre Dame Press, 1983, pp. 92-112.

the messianic movement, individuals risk merely performing roles—like those described in *Who Am I?*—roles shaped and sustained by a moralistic and metaphysical approach to reality.¹⁷

Larry Rasmussen¹⁸ poses an important question about whether the concepts of *formation* and *command* in Bonhoeffer's ethics represent distinct approaches or merely variations of a single method. He suggests that "ethics as formation" may be the more fundamental and enduring concept in Bonhoeffer's thought. Offering a different perspective, Stephen Plant¹⁹ argues that Bonhoeffer engages ethics in two grammatical moods: the subjunctive, representing ethics as formation, and the imperative, reflecting the ethics of command. This distinction highlights the dynamic interplay in Bonhoeffer's work between moral development shaped by community and Christ-likeness, and the direct, sometimes urgent, call to responsible action.

Another perspective is offered by Heinrich Ott, who argues that Bonhoeffer advocates for a situational ethic. Ott asks, "What happens to ethics at the collapse of 'natural law' or 'natural morality,' as a system of pronouncements to be applied to each case as it arises?"²⁰ He suggests that Bonhoeffer's approach moves away from a casuistic model and leans toward what he describes as a "pure situation ethic." In contrast, Harold Lockley²¹ interprets Bonhoeffer's ethical project as a search for a *concrete ethic*—one that integrates the strengths of both a situationist approach and a normative framework. Lockley sees Bonhoeffer as attempting to hold together the contextual sensitivity of situation ethics with the moral clarity of normative principles, without collapsing into either extreme. This dual emphasis reflects Bonhoeffer's broader commitment to responsible action grounded in the reality of Christ and the complexities of lived experience.

17 Hans D. Van Hoogstraten, "Ethics and the Problem of Metaphysics," in *Theology and the Practice of Responsibility: Essays on Dietrich Bonhoeffer*, eds. Wayne Whitson Floyd, Jr. and Charles Marsh, Valley Ford: PA, Trinity Press, 1994, p. 228.

18 Larry Rasmussen, "A Question of Method," in *New Studies in Bonhoeffer's Ethics*, ed. William J. Peck, Lewiston, Edwin Mellen Press, 1987, pp. 103-138.

19 Stephen Plant, *Bonhoeffer*, London, Continuum, 2004, pp. 118-124.

20 Heinrich Ott, *Reality and Faith: The Theological Legacy of Dietrich Bonhoeffer*, London, Lutterworth, 1971, p. 257.

21 Harold Lockley, *Dietrich Bonhoeffer: His Ethics and its Value for Christian Ethics Today*, Swansea, Phoenix Press, 1993, p. 27.

James Burtness adds another layer to the interpretation of Bonhoeffer's ethics by identifying elements not only of situational ethics but also of consequentialism. He highlights Bonhoeffer's consistent emphasis on the responsibility for future outcomes, stating: "The emphasis upon the future places Bonhoeffer with those ethicists who concentrate on the consequences of actions rather than the motives out of which the actions are done. It is not the rightness of an action but the result of an action which commends it."²² For Burtness, Bonhoeffer's ethical reasoning is marked by a pragmatic concern for the real-world impact of decisions, rather than strict adherence to moral intentions or abstract principles. This focus reinforces Bonhoeffer's broader theme of *responsible action*—an ethic grounded in accountability, context, and the recognition that discipleship often demands difficult choices in morally complex situations.

Bonhoeffer's vision of peacemakers

Even as war loomed on the horizon, Bonhoeffer remained deeply preoccupied with the question of peace. In a speech delivered at the ecumenical conference in Fano, he articulated a vision of the Church that transcends national and political divisions. He declared that the Church of Christ "is spread among all peoples ... and transcends ethnic, political, social or racial boundaries." On that basis, he issued a radical call: "The Church must take the weapons from the hands of her sons ... and forbid war to them."²³ This statement reflects Bonhoeffer's commitment to a peace grounded not in political calculation, but in the universal and reconciling nature of the body of Christ. It also underscores his belief that the Church must actively resist becoming an instrument of nationalist violence.

Bonhoeffer's *The Cost of Discipleship* is a forceful call to obey Christ fully—even when that obedience demands suffering and sacrifice. Central to the book is his condemnation of what he terms "cheap grace," which he defines as grace without discipleship, without the cross, and without Jesus Christ truly lived. Bonhoeffer writes, "Cheap grace is the mortal enemy of our church. Today, our struggle is for the grace that

22 James Burtness, *Shaping the Future: The Ethics of Dietrich Bonhoeffer*, Minneapolis, Fortress Press, 1985, p. 16.

23 Bonhoeffer, *Costul uceniciei*, p. 14.

costs dearly.”²⁴ This costly grace, he explains, demands everything: “It is costly because it calls us to discipleship... because it costs a man his life... above all, it is costly because it was expensive for God, because it cost God the life of His Son.”²⁵ The death of Christ, for Bonhoeffer, was the price of our reconciliation with the Father—a cost that underscores the seriousness of Christian commitment. Alongside this call to radical discipleship, Bonhoeffer places a strong emphasis on peace. “The disciples of Jesus are called to peace,” he writes, and “with their call by Jesus, they found peace. Jesus is their peace”²⁶ Yet peace is not only something to be received; it is something to be made. Bonhoeffer insists that Jesus’ followers “are called not only to have, but also to make peace,”²⁷ reflecting a life that mirrors the reconciling mission of Christ in both word and action.²⁸

For Bonhoeffer, being a peacemaker isn’t optional—it’s a calling.²⁹ “The disciples of Jesus are called to peace,”³⁰ he writes, underscoring that peace is not just a personal virtue but a demand placed on every follower of Christ. First and foremost, the disciples’ calling is to be personally reconciled to Jesus, for “Jesus is their peace.”³¹ This reconciliation forms the foundation of their identity and mission. Having received peace through Christ, they are not only called to live in that peace but also to become agents of it. Peacemaking, in Bonhoeffer’s view, is not a passive state but an active task rooted in the reality of their relationship with Christ.³² The disciples are summoned to bring peace into a world marked by division and hostility, reflecting the very peace they themselves have received.

How can this be done practically? Practically, Bonhoeffer argues that peacemaking is carried out through the “renunciation of force and

24 Bonhoeffer, *Costul uceniciei*, p. 31.

25 Bonhoeffer, *Costul uceniciei*, p. 33.

26 Bonhoeffer, *Costul uceniciei*, p. 99.

27 Bonhoeffer, *Costul uceniciei*, p. 99.

28 Jennifer Lynne Moberly, *The Virtue of Bonhoeffer’s Ethics: A Study of Dietrich Bonhoeffer’s Ethics in Relation to virtue Ethics* (Durham theses, Durham University. Available at Durham E-Theses

Online: <http://etheses.dur.ac.uk/89/>), pp. 115-142.

29 Charles Marsh, *Reclaiming Dietrich Bonhoeffer: The Promise of His Theology*, Oxford, Oxford University Press, 1994, pp. 68-70.

30 Bonhoeffer, *Costul uceniciei*, p. 99.

31 Bonhoeffer, *Costul uceniciei*, p. 99.

32 Marsh, *Reclaiming Dietrich Bonhoeffer*, pp. 81-107.

rebellion.”³³ For him, these methods are incompatible with the character of the kingdom of God. Rather than advancing God’s reign, violence and insurrection obstruct it. This is because the kingdom is not built through coercion or power struggles, but through the presence and practice of peace. To use force is to deny the very nature of the kingdom disciples are called to embody. In rejecting violence, disciples bear witness to a different kind of power—one that reflects the peace of Christ. Bonhoeffer further states: „Jesus’ disciples maintain peace by choosing to suffer themselves rather than causing others to suffer. They preserve fellowship even when others break it, let go of self-righteousness, and refuse to retaliate when faced with hatred and injustice.”³⁴ As an argument, Bonhoeffer quotes from Romans 12:21.

In conclusion, Bonhoeffer describes peacemaking disciples as those who embody and enact God’s peace: “Therefore, they are makers of divine peace, in the midst of a world torn by hatred and war.”³⁵ Their task is not merely to wish for peace but to actively pursue it—through self-sacrifice, reconciliation, and a refusal to answer violence with violence. In doing so, they reflect the very nature of Christ and become visible signs of the kingdom of God in a fractured world.³⁶ Even if they suffer from people.

Conclusions

Otniel Bunaciu raises a pressing contemporary question: “How should a Christian relate to violence and war in today’s world?” He observes that “what we could call Christendom in its European forms was not able to claim the blessing of being a peacemaker as Jesus promised.”³⁷ This critique highlights the historical failure of institutional Christianity to embody the radical peace ethic of the Gospel, particularly in contexts of conflict. Nevertheless, Bunaciu affirms that Christians are still called to

33 Bonhoeffer, *Costul uceniciei*, p. 99.

34 Bonhoeffer, *Costul uceniciei*, p. 99.

35 Bonhoeffer, *Costul uceniciei*, p. 99.

36 Ioan-Gheorghe Rotaru, “Precum Eu v-am iubit pe voi, să vă iubiți unul pe altul!” (“As I have loved you, that you also love one another!”), *Argeșul orthodox*, IX, 2010, nr. 467, p. 7.

37 Otniel Bunaciu, “Blessed Are the Peacemaker ...”: A Reflection on Karl Barth’s Understanding on War and Peace from A Perspective of the Situation in Europa Today,” in *Jurnal teologic (Theological journal)*, Vol. 22, Nr. 2 (2023), p. 44.

be agents of peace—even in times of crisis or war. The call to peacemaking, grounded in the teachings and example of Jesus, remains a central responsibility of Christian discipleship regardless of political or social conditions.

In a time marked by violence and ideological conflict, Bonhoeffer's vision of Christian ethical responsibility remains strikingly countercultural. For him, to be a peacemaker is not to retreat from conflict, but to engage it with a radically different posture—one shaped by the life, death, and peace of Christ. Peacemaking requires not only a rejection of violence and rebellion, but a deep commitment to reconciliation, even at great personal cost. In wartime, when the world defaults to force, the disciple is called to witness to another reality—the kingdom of God, characterized not by domination, but by peace. Bonhoeffer's challenge endures: true discipleship means bearing the cross of peace in a world at war.

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